

This repository contains the data, scripts and codes used for the work entitled “**Handling of spurious sequences affects the outcome of high-throughput 16S rRNA gene amplicon profiling**” by Reitmeier et al. published in ISME Communications.

The 16S rRNA gene amplicon datasets generated in the present study are available in the European Nucleotide Archive (www.ebi.ac.uk/ena) under study accession number PRJEB34431 (data from the Microbiome Core Facility of ZIEL) and SRA accession numbers SRR10688001-37 (data from the JMF) and PRJNA659641 (data from RWTH Aachen).

The content of the repository is sorted by Figures, according to the backbone of the published manuscript, as follows:

Figure 2

Figure_2_Analysis_Description.txt

- Description of the OTU data analysis workflow used for Plot 2a-e

Figure_2e-f_ASV-analysis (Folder)

- Raw and pre-processed data for the ASV analysis
- Script for calculation of the richness for each of the filtering thresholds
- Script for identification of the spurious ASVs

Figure_2a-e.R

- Script generating boxplots for the prevalence of spurious taxa and positive hits

Figure_2f (Folder)

- R-Script for the creation of input data
- R-Script and input tables for plotting

Figure 3

Figure_3_Analysis_Description.pdf

- Description of the data analysis of Figure 3a-d

Figure_3_Data_and_pre-processing (Folder)

- Spurious sequences of 10 Mock communities and their clustering at 97% similarity

Figure_3a (Folder)

- Data for generation of taxonomic tree in iTOL

Figure_3b (Folder)

- Data for plot of spurious OTUs distribution

Figure_3c (Folder)

- Data for plotting run-dependent prevalence of spurious OTUs in Mock samples

Figure_3d (Folder)

- Data and R-Script for the generation of violin plots

Figure_3e (Folder)

- R-Script and input files for plotting the bar plots

Figure 4

Figure_4a.R

- R-Script generating bar plot including inter-quartile range

Figure_4b (Folder)

- Pre-processed data and scripts to identify inter- and intra-run variations

Figure_4c (Folder)

- R-Script and input files to generate the dot plot of richness at increasing sequencing depth

Figure 5

Figure_5_Analysis_Description.txt

- Analysis description

Figure_5a.R

- R-Script to generate individual-specific distance plots of microbiota profiles over time

Figure_5b.R

- R-Script to generate distance plots for patient groups

Figure 6

Figure_6.md

- Description of data retrieval and analysis